

ESTABLISHMENT AND OPERATION OF THE FIRST ELDERS' CARE INSTITUTION IN ALBANIA¹

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Introduction

This article analyses the efforts for establishing and operating the first elders' care institutions in Albania during the monarchical regime of Ahmet Zogu and the fascist occupation, when the first such institution was established. The article is based on archival documents researched and collected in the Central Archive of the Albanian State, the Red Cross archival funds, the Prime Minister's Office, the Ministry of the Interior, Finance, Justice, Sub-prefectures/prefectures, and municipalities. Based on those documents, a detailed description is given of the efforts of the Albanian authorities to found a care institution for the elderly, of the taxes collected for this purpose, of the negotiations between the central and the local institutions during the process, of the justifications encouraging the payments of these taxes made by the state representatives.

In addition, a comparative analysis is made of the main dimensions of the social care with the social care conceptualized and provided by the Albanian state. The concept of social care is broader than that for the elderly, but in this article, only social care for the elderly is considered. As will be presented below, the basic concept of Albanian state is that the main provider of elders' care is the family. Only a few individuals, who do not have family or stable incomes, should be taken care of by the state institutions and their care would be paid through special taxes.

As it may be understood from the aforementioned documentary funds, this article is based mainly on an official perspective of looking at the social condition of the elderly and of the efforts to establish an institution for them in Albania. This

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The term used by the Albanian authorities for the institutions that would house the elderly and disabled, is "asylum" (*azil*). This term continues to be used also during the period of socialism, while after the fall of the socialist regime in Albania, the term "home for the elderly" is adopted. In the English terminology, the most used term for elders' care institutions is "nursing homes", however, less often "elders home" is also used. Considering that the concept of care for the elderly has changed a lot since the 1930s, the author of this article has chosen to use the term "elder's care institution", which is a neutral term. Also interchangeable in the text can be found the use of the terms "elders' house", "elders' care house". The word "house" is preferred instead of "home" because *house* has a less emotional connotation than *home*, which also includes the family aspect, and in our opinion, it responds better to the approach of the authorities of the time to those institutions and the elders in them.

is because, due to the time distance, it is not possible to conduct interviews with the individuals housed in these institutions. Also, in a country where illiteracy was over ninety percent, especially for the elderly and poor people, there are no documents such as diaries or correspondence from the residents of these institutions. On the other hand, as will be seen below, in a country of growing poverty, in the absence of private charitable institutions, the state is forced to take on the role of social care for those social categories.

On the dimensions of social care and its relationship with the welfare state

Social care is a concept that implies multiple dimensions. One of them is that care is considered a kind of labour, and here also comes the role of the state in determining if this labour is paid, unpaid, formal or informal. Another question is who is responsible for providing the care. The most common answer to this question has been the family, and in rarer cases, society, community, religious institutions. With the entry of the welfare state into the scene, these providers can change, be reinforced or re-dimensioned, which is often determined by the state agents. A third element very important to understand social care is who pays for it. Is the cost of social care borne by private institutions or by public ones? These two big categories have other sub-categories such as the individual, the family, the wider family circle, the small community, charitable institutions, society as a whole, or the state (Daly & Lewis, 2000, p. 285).

If the welfare state were analysed from social care perspective, then the analysis would include several dimensions at macro and micro levels. Perhaps the most important dimension at the macro level is which of the social or political factors such as the family, the community, the state or the market, will bear the greatest responsibility for social care. Another dimension at the macro level is what is the infrastructure and means, by which social care is carried out, is it carried out at home, in public institutions, in community centres, and in what way: by giving money directly to those who need it, or by offering services. At the micro level, the analysis focuses on who are the individuals who provide care, what are the gender roles within a family in this respect. In public institutions, how care is distributed between the different genders, what are the relationships between beneficiaries and providers of care in families and institutions, under which specific economic conditions an individual becomes a beneficiary of social care provided by the state (Daly & Lewis, 2000, pp. 286-288).

Traditionally, policy makers, even in the most developed welfare states, are determined to share roles and responsibilities between the family and the state for providing care. The majority of policy makers, even in the case of countries with a large welfare state benefits, usually do not question the role of the family as the greatest care provider. The state is seen more as a redistributor of income through fiscal policies, than as a direct provider of services. Thus, in general, countries with social policies have mainly provided financial resources for disabled individuals than social care services. However, in terms of elderly care, the state investment for institutional care is introduced earlier than other forms of institutional social care (Daly & Lewis, 2018, pp. 9-10).

Historical background of social care institutions in Albania

Albania has no tradition in state health and social care institutions. This is because it is the last country in the Balkans to gain independence, thus it develops state institutions relatively late. It cannot be said that there were no health and social care institutions in the Ottoman Empire, but the Albanian lands were the most peripheral, and the most underdeveloped part of the empire, therefore public investments for such institutions were very few. Larger public investments at that time were for public schools and government buildings (Caka, 2021, p. 59).

Also, from the time the Albanian state gains independence (November 1912) until 1920, the organizational capacities of the Albanian state are very limited, since the central state institutions exist only *de jure*, as during the First Balkan War and the First World War Albania becomes a battlefield between warring foreign powers. Consequently, there is no central power that could exercise its functions, let alone strive for the establishment of social care institutions.

In the period of the Ottoman Empire, even in the first years of the existence of the Albanian state, the role of social caregivers for poor individuals play the religious institutions of all religions in Albania. Thus, mosques, dervish shrines, Orthodox monasteries and Catholic convents, as part of their religious and social activities, also maintain institutions such as alms-houses for the poor, shelters for orphaned children, shelters for elderly people without relatives, shelters for refugees and hospitals for the sick (Xhuvani & Haxhillazi, 2007, p. 272). Those institutions are financially supported through the waqf system, according to which religious institutions keep and administer properties for their needs, as well as for charity. This system is highly dependent on the charitable gifts that wealthy people give to the religious institutions, either during their lifetime or by will after their death (Caka, 2021, p. 130). However, these shelters are not permanent, as the people who are accommodated there do not stay for a long time, but rather for immediate needs, especially hunger or extreme illness. The most stable social institutions founded by the religious communities in Albania in that period are the institutions, established and maintained by the Stigmantine sisters in Shkodër (Dioqeza e Sapës, n.d.).

There are also shelters and canteens for poor people set up and maintained by rich individuals or families with private initiative. In Albania, in this respect there has been a tradition, although limited, where wealthy families or individuals, following the religious values of mercy, almsgiving, compassion and caring for the poor, help the poor, give free food in their houses, especially on certain days of the week (Friday, Sunday), or on religious holidays. They also take poor orphaned children to whom they provide shelter, food and living conditions. However, in the period of the National Renaissance and the first decades of the Albanian state, the biggest donations of rich people to the community are for education. This is because Albanians lack education in their national language in the Ottoman Empire, and one of the main tools announced by the National Renaissance for raising national consciousness is education. However, just like the social institutions established and maintained by religious communities, those are also based on voluntariness, and are not sustainable. It often happens that from one

generation to the next this tradition is lost, as children do not always have the good will of their parents or grandparents to perform acts of charity for the poor. Thus, although these practices help to somewhat alleviate the social problems of the population in the country, they are not sustainable (Hoxha, 2011, pp. 5-10).

The first public institution of social care established in Albania in 1917 is an orphanage in Tirana for orphaned and poor children whose parents are killed during the war. This orphan shelter is built during the First World War, when Albania is turned into a battlefield, therefore there is a large number of displaced people, refugees, people left without a house and especially orphaned children. Thus, this orphan shelter is built in a collaboration between the vice-prefect Rauf Fico and the mayor of Tirana Zyber Hallulli, as well as the Red Cross organizations that operate at that time in the country. However, the institution, although established by the municipality of Tirana, functions more like a private institution, which is maintained on the incomes donated by the mayor himself, by the Tirana community, by voluntary donations, by religious communities or by wealthy individuals (RTV Klan, 2017).

The Red Cross also makes an important contribution to social care in the period of the new formation of the Albanian state. Together with the warring Austro-Hungarian, Italian, French and other armies in Albania during the First World War, the Red Cross organizations of those countries also come, which provides a great deal of help to mitigate the problems caused by their armies. Also, after the end of the Great War, a significant effort is done by the American Red Cross, which, together with the Albanian diaspora in the USA, help a lot to cure the consequences of the War in Albania (Kryqi i Kuq Shqiptar, n.d.).

The period 1920–1939 is also a period of the Albanian state's consolidation, especially after 1925, when power returns to the hands of Ahmet Zogu, who is proclaimed king in 1928. During this period, when the central institutions of the Albanian state are integrated, the first beginnings of educational, health and social care institutions in Albania are also established. In 1921, the Albanian Red Cross is founded, which takes over the administration of the children's orphanage. In cooperation with other associations of the International League of the Red Cross and the Albanian diaspora, it also helps Albanian refugees from the neighbouring countries, as well as other needy groups in the country, such as poor children and the elderly, lonely and without support, who are given free food, clothing, and health care. During the reign of Ahmet Zogu, one of his sisters, Sanije Zogu, becomes the patroness of the Red Cross, and under her auspices several steps are taken to continue the activities of the Red Cross (Kryqi i Kuq Shqiptar, n.d.).

In the period after 1920–1925, when the Albanian state is fully consolidated, there is a significant decrease in charitable donations, especially those for educational purposes. This is because with the establishment of the Albanian state, the responsibility of establishing and maintaining national education is placed in the hands of the state. However, there is no shift of charitable aid from education to health or social issues, but rather, there is a general decrease in charity (Hoxha, 2011, pp. 55-56).

Efforts for establishing an elders' care institution in Albania

The issue of establishing an elders' care institution in Albania is raised by the institutions of the Albanian state since 1936. Thus, in April 1936, at the initiative of the Ministry of the Interior, a Commission is set up, consisting of representatives of this ministry, the municipality of Tirana, the Council of State and the Ministry of Justice and Finance. The Commission's task is to examine the possibilities and to do the feasibility study for the establishment of such institution. The reason for this initiative is that in 1936 Albania is greatly affected by the financial crisis with increasing poverty, many elderly people live in absolute misery and without shelter, and also there is a lack of private charitable institutions (CSA, F:380, fl.340, p.1, 1936).

As there are many old people in the country who live alone, are sick, very poor and have no other means of living, and as a result of the work of this commission, a decision is made by the royal government with which the Albanian Red Cross is charged with the task of establishing in the capital and in other Albanian towns institutions for housing the elderly who have no other livelihood and care. According to the provisions of the Civil Code of 1929, children have the duty to support and feed their elderly parents (Pellumbi, 2019, p. 4). Likewise, able-bodied people had the duty to keep and take care of other elderly relatives who "live under the same roof" with them (without determining to what degree of family relations). Thus, in the royal decree on the establishment of houses for the elderly, they are determined for "elderly people of both sexes, who are disabled, have no means of living, cannot work, and do not have relatives who can support them, according to the provisions of the Civil Code" (CSA, F:147, fl. 665. pp.2-3, 1938).

The same decree also defines that a special medical facility should function within each of the houses for the elderly, and it should serve for the treatment and necessary health care for the elderly or the disabled. In accordance with this, there should also be a doctor as a member of the institution's staff. Those institutions should be managed by a director appointed by a royal decree at the proposal of the Red Cross. For the smooth running of those houses for the elderly, a special regulation is approved, which defines their functioning, the recruitment and duties of their personnel, as well as the acceptance of the elderly, their treatment and living conditions (CSA, F:147, fl. 665. pp.2-3, 1938).

Of special importance in the decision to establish houses for the elderly is the determination that these institutions are public and are maintained with special taxes collected for the purpose. The importance of this determination is because until that time, as described above, except for the orphanage, there are no social care institutions supported by state income. Historically, social care in Albania is exercised first by the family or by religious institutions, or on a voluntary basis by individuals and wealthy families. Meanwhile, the orphanage is established in Tirana by the municipality of Tirana, also under the auspices of the Red Cross, but no special taxes are determined for its maintenance and it is based on voluntary donations or allocated funds by the state budget. As for the establishment and maintenance of houses for the elderly, special public taxes are imposed for the benefit of the Albanian Red Cross, so that there is a change towards the establishment and strengthening of public institutions.

In an announcement of the Council of Ministers, some taxes for maintaining houses for the elderly are determined. One of the reasons why the state is forced to set special taxes for the budget of old people's houses is that private donations to the Red Cross are completely negligible in the general budget of the institution, which could not survive without state support (Hoxha, 2011, p. 57). At a time when there is no private charitable initiative, which could alleviate social wounds, state bodies are forced to intervene and exercise that role.

Eight types of taxes are established for the budget of the Red Cross in order to found and maintain houses for the elderly. To the price of the Red Cross tax stamps, the income of which is collected directly by the institution, a value of 0.20 gold francs is added, which should go only to the budget of these institutions. An annual tax of 15 gold francs should be levied from each radio set in public places such as cafes, restaurants, clubs, theatres and other first class entertainment facilities, while for radios in similar places categorized as lower class an annual tax of 10 gold francs should be levied. A 10% for the Red Cross should be added to the taxes collected by municipalities for gaming facilities, such as billiards, backgammon, chess and card games. In addition, 2% should be added to the construction permit taxes issued by the municipalities. A 10% should be added to the taxes once collected for the granting of a permit to practice regulated professions, such as lawyers, doctors, notaries, pharmacists, candidates for parliament. Those taxes are collected by central institutions such as the Ministry of Justice, Finance or National Economy, and should be also passed directly to the budget of the Red Cross. A tax is added to cinema and theatre tickets, 0.05 gold francs for tickets worth less than one gold franc, and 0.10 gold francs for tickets that cost one franc or more. A fixed tax of one franc should be added to the taxes levied on insurances of 1,000 gold francs and above. Also, 5% for the Red Cross budget should be added to the taxes for deposit stamps. The Ministry of Internal Affairs, the Ministry of Finance and the Ministry of Public Works are responsible for collecting those taxes. Setting taxes for the establishment and maintenance of institutions for elders' care is a moment when the Albanian state shows features of a welfare state, which redistributes funding through taxes and provides social care. Also, in the same decision, it is determined that the activity of the Red Cross, such as its payments and the management of its assets, should be exempt from all taxes. Meanwhile, the Red Cross is allowed to accept gifts in cash and real estate in order to build and maintain houses for the elderly (CSA, F:147, fl. 665. pp.2-3, 1938).

This last point of the Council of Ministers' decision is different from some previous decisions regarding donations for the maintenance of other institutions, such as religious or educational ones. Thus, the law forbids the religious institutions to receive donations from abroad or by foreign citizens, and for Albanian citizens there is a limit of 1000 golden francs. This is done in order to avoid foreign influence on religion (Bello, 2017, p. 149). Likewise, in the year 1933 the state nationalizes all private schools, making education a state monopoly. This is done in order to stop the transmission of foreign ideologies to Albanian students, because the sources of income of private schools come from abroad. This is looked upon with suspicion by the Albanian state, considering it as a means for the denationalization of the young generation (Bello, 2017, pp. 149-150).

This prohibition does not exist for the old people's houses; donations from within or from outside are even encouraged, although they are few. As it appears from the communication of the Minister of the Interior with the Prime Minister, the Minister of Justice and Finance, unlike youth, elders could not be in any danger, since the old people could not be influenced by the foreign, anti-national ideology. The elders are considered almost inactive beings, who cannot be dangerous for the state; they just need to be taken care of in the last days of their life.

In cooperation between the Ministry of Finance and the Ministry of Internal Affairs, all prefectures are ordered to ensure the collecting of the above-mentioned taxes and over-taxes for the formation of the budget for houses for the elderly (CSA, F: 178, fl.2250, p. 3-5, 1938).

From the correspondence with those institutions, it can be seen that there is a resistance to these additional taxes from the tax subjects, such as the owners of the premises, the practitioners of free professions, or those who requested a construction permit. Thus, several mayors in the municipalities of Kavaja and Fier write to the relevant sub-prefectures and the Ministry of the Interior and the Ministry of Finance, regarding the resistance of the owners of the premises to the collection of the radio tax for the benefit of the Red Cross (CSA, F:266, fl.129, pp.2-3, 1939), (CSA, F:223_2, fl. 69, p.7-10, 1939).

It is interesting to note that in the response of the Ministry of the Interior, state officials are advised, before taking disciplinary measures against those who resisted, to do "propaganda" by appealing to the conscience of those owners and explaining how with these small surcharges they would help all those lonely and disabled old people, who have no means of livelihood or relatives to care for them, to break away from the extreme poverty and to remove from the street, from begging and from the risk of starvation. "This should be proclaimed as a spiritual and patriotic duty for the common good of the entire society that honours our nation" (CSA, F.223_2, fl.69, p. 90-91, 1939).

Also, in the same period, the Council of Ministers orders the Ministry of Finance to issue a series of postage stamps for the benefit of the Red Cross. These stamps should have six series, 2, 5, 10, 15, 25 and 50 pennies, and should be printed by the Ministry of Finance at the expense of the Red Cross, to whose benefit the income should also go. In another decision of the Ministry of Finance, a public printing house in Tirana is ordered to print those stamps with a circulation of 20,000 pieces. These should be sold in the offices of the Albanian Post, but also by private sellers. The Red Cross in its turn does not have the right to use these revenues for other expenses, except for building and maintaining houses for the elderly (CSA, F:478, fl. 670, p.20, 1938).

In addition, there was also a communication between the Ministry of Finance, the Ministry of Internal Affairs and the sub-prefecture of Lushnja, where most of the state farms are located, to transfer 5% from their incomes directly to the budget of the Red Cross (CSA, F.225, fl.34 pp.1-3, 1939).

These are the first steps of the Albanian state in establishing a care institution for the elderly in the country. Throughout 1938, the Albanian government is mainly concerned with collecting funds for the budget of the Red Cross for houses for the elderly. In February 1939, the regulation of the Council of Ministers on the operation of elders' care institutions is approved. According to the regulation, these

institutions could accept elderly and disabled people of both sexes, who have no means of livelihood, are unable to work and have no relatives who should support them according to the law. Abandoned children up to the age of four could be also temporarily accepted, after which they should be sent to orphanage. The houses should be administered by the Red Cross and should be supported by its budget, formed from the aforementioned income. The number of people admitted to those institutions should be determined on the basis of the annual income of the Red Cross.

The regulation also sets the application procedure for the old people's houses. The old person should make a written request to the Red Cross office. As accompanying documents, one should have a certificate of civil status, a certificate of poverty, which is issued by the municipality and certifies that the person seeking to enter the house for the elderly meets the above-mentioned conditions to be admitted to them. This should be verified by the relevant Prefecture or Sub/prefecture. Priority is given to the elderly over the age of 60 and those who are disabled. Elderly people with mental illnesses or leprosy, as well as those who have contagious diseases without being completely cured, are not accepted in the nursing houses. For this reason, before any admission to elders' houses, each candidate should be examined by a medical committee. Once a year, the elders' house committee receives the list of candidates from the Red Cross Directorate and decides on each case. When someone is admitted to the old people's house, one is registered in the registry of the institution and dressed in their uniform. Small workshops operate near the old people's houses, in which various crafts could be practiced for the benefit of the institution, and the items produced there could be sold increasing its income. Likewise, the elderly who are able to do small jobs should be involved in the internal affairs of the institution. The jobs and the crafts they could practice should be determined by the director under the advice of the relevant doctor. In this way, it is ordered that the elderly should work to partly cover the internal expenses of the old people's houses. The regulation also determines that if it is discovered that any of the elderly admitted to the institution has relatives who are legally responsible for him/her, then the old person should be sent to them (CSA, F:203, fl. 940, p.1-5, 1939).

As can be seen from the documents referred to above, the operation of the houses for the elderly and the admission of the elderly to them is well defined by the regulation and quite detailed in every aspect. What can be observed here is that the bureaucracy of admission to those institutions is quite complicated: a written request and two certificates are required, one personal and one of poverty issued by the municipality and certified by the prefecture. For all these procedures, it is necessary to pay the relevant service fees and they require time to be implemented. Moreover, in a country where illiteracy reaches more than 80% of the population, writing and reading and dealing with the relevant bureaucratic procedures requires additional expenses. In fact, in that period in Albania, writing requests and dealing with government affairs is practiced as a public profession. There are certain scribes, relatively educated persons who, for payment, carry out bureaucratic procedures of interested people who are illiterate and could not follow the official steps. However, considering the category of people eligible for these institutions, payment for those procedures is an additional cost, which makes it difficult for most of the needy elderly to follow the admission procedure.

Another element of this regulation is the fact that a very limited category of elderly people is accepted in nursing houses, those who are extremely poor, disabled and who have no other means of living, that is, according to the definition of the Council of Ministers of the time, those elderly “who really deserve it”. Even if the elderly meet those criteria, they would not always be admitted to the institutions, depending on the available places, so the solution of this problem is half-hearted. This is also related to the fact that the financial opportunities of the state are very limited. Albania is always in difficulty to meet the budget needs and constantly depends on loans and Italian aid, especially after the crisis in 1933 and the return of many emigrants from France and the USA to the country. However, it should be considered that in a politically tense situation, with a lack of stability in the domestic and international political arena, the central bodies of the Albanian state try to manage the country’s social problems.

Also, in the period February–March 1939, there is correspondence between the Ministry of the Interior, the Ministry of Finance and several municipalities and prefectures regarding the rigorous implementation of the collection of taxes for the budget and the houses for the elderly, as well as directives for the transfer of these taxes to the budget of the Red Cross (CSA, F: 246, fl.175, pp.2-3, 1939).

Italian occupation and the foundation of elders’ care institution in Albania

On 7 April 1939, Albania is invaded by Italy and an Assembly unites the crowns between Albania and Italy, after which the harmonization of Albanian and Italian legislation begins. This procedure is not too difficult, since even during the period of the Kingdom of Zogu due to the ties between the two countries the Albanian laws follow the Italian ones (Fischer, 2012). In general, there is a continuity in the institutions, orders and regulations from the Zogu regime to the fascist one, if only because most of the state administration at all levels is the same.

Thus, in August 1939, a decree is issued by Viceroy Francesco Jacomoni, which orders the continuation of collecting the taxes for the budget of the old people’s houses, as well as the implementation of the decision to establish them with the same regulation as that of February 1939 of Zogu’s government (CSA, F:147, fl:5, p.1-2., 1939).

Similarly, in the ordinance and the communications of the Prime Minister Shefqet Vërlaci with the Ministry of Finance and the Interior, it refers to the same decision and regulation. The Prime Minister instructs those ministries to order the municipalities to continue rigorously collecting taxes for the benefit of the Red Cross for the budget of old people’s houses, as this is an important social problem that cannot be left behind (CSA, F:149, fl.45, pp.10-12, 1939).

The Red Cross Directorate, in communication with the Albanian Post and the Monopoly Stamps Directorate, requests that according to the order of the Prime Minister and the Ministry of Finance, and in accordance with the Viceroy’s decree, the sale of stamps as well as the transfer to the budget of this institution of income from taxes collected by the municipalities should continue in order to found and maintain houses for the elderly. Thus, it can be observed that there is a continuity

in the plans for establishing a house for the elderly of the Albanian political leaders from the period of the Monarchy to that of the fascist occupation. The rhetoric is the same as well: the initiative is justified with the difficulties faced by the elderly and the disabled in the country, and this is considered a social duty of all Albanians (CSA, F:149, fl.45, pp.10-12, 1939).

However, from these governmental orders to the day of establishing the first house for the elderly in Albania almost a year would pass. The government's decision in May 1940 announces that three old people's houses would be built in Albania, taking care of their geographical distribution: one in Shkodër in the north, one in Tirana as the capital, and one in Vlora in the south (CSA, F:149, fl. 18, pp.7-8, 1940). However, due to financial reasons, this becomes impossible and it is decided to build only one house for the elderly in Shkodër. In July 1940, the Viceroy's decree is announced to establish a house for the elderly in Shkodër with 90 places and with three sectors: one for elderly men, one for women, and one for abandoned children up to the age of four. Admission to the house is provided according to the aforementioned regulation. An already existing building is used after the necessary refurbishment. The Directorate of the Red Cross makes a public tender for the renovation of the old building, as well as for its equipment with beds, mattresses, and other items. Thus, in July 1940, the house for the elderly in Shkodër, the only one in Albania, begins to function for the first time (CSA, F:203, fl. 944, pp.20-30, 1940).

Regarding the establishment of the first house for the elderly in Albania, it takes a long time from the beginning of the Albanian government's plans to their actual implementation. From the formation of a commission to examine this issue in 1936 until the establishment of the house in 1940 four years pass. Moreover, it takes about two years from the issuance of the law on the establishment of houses for the elderly and making a budget for them, up to its actual establishment. There are objective reasons for this. Albania is a poor country with budgetary difficulties to meet the needs of the people and public investments are limited. The very issue of a law for collecting taxes and special over-taxes for the budget of houses for the elderly shows the inability of the Albanian government to allocate funds from the existing budget for the establishment of such houses. Also, there is resistance on the part of the subjects of these taxes for their collection, which is explained by the same economic crisis that has put the budget of the Albanian state in difficulty. Consumption in the country has decreased considerably and the entities from which these taxes should be levied has a lot of difficulties to maintain their functioning. However, the state institutions continue collecting taxes in 1938–1940 constituting the budget for old people's houses.

Another element that influences the postponement of the construction of houses for the elderly in the country is the occupation of Albania by Fascist Italy, which for a while suspends the state administration's activity. The decrees and orders of the previous government are reconfirmed by the new administration. The state orders receive a continuity and the Quisling government instructs the continuation of the efforts to build a house for the elderly.

The arrival of the Italian army improves the general economy of Albania, since in order to reduce popular resistance against the invaders, the Italians make large public investments, bring a significant financial aid and the arrival of Italian

soldiers increases the consumption, since they buy local products. Also, from the very beginning, the Italians undertake wide health and social care campaigns, open vaccination points for contagious diseases, mobile hospitals for the population are set up in every part of Albania. Public canteens are also opened where the locals could go, also citizens could eat in the canteens of the army barracks. However, those steps of the Italians do not solve the major problems of poverty in Albania, moreover, these are only temporary solutions (Fischer, 1999).

Since the first news about the establishment of a house for the elderly in Shkodër spreads, the Red Cross Directorate in Tirana begins to receive requests from elderly people to be admitted to this institution. Attached to these requests are also the corresponding poverty certificates, which are issued by the respective municipalities and certified by the prefectures or sub-prefectures. Thus, in March 1940, an old woman sends a request to the Red Cross, in which she explains she has heard that an institution for the elderly will be opened in Shkodër, that she is a poor old woman without any relatives and without means of living, so she asks to be accepted in this asylum (CSA, F: 346, fl. 153, pp. 1-5, 1940).

Likewise, throughout the year 1940, there are requests from poor old people who seek shelter in the old people's house in Shkodër, justifying this with their advanced age, lack of relatives to take care of them, extreme poverty, the inability to work and the lack of other means of living. What is observed in these efforts of the elderly to be admitted to these institutions is their dragging through various administration offices to obtain the relevant documents. This is made even more difficult when those citizens do not have the civil status register in the town where they live, as they have moved there without obtaining the relevant documents. Cases like these are often encountered, especially for the elderly who live as homeless beggars, since they come to the bigger towns to have somewhat more opportunities for living and housing. Thus, there are cases when citizens in the municipality of Durrës or Berat request poverty certificates from the respective municipalities, but it is impossible for the municipalities to issue those documents due to the lack of their registration in the civil status registers (CSA, F: 235, fl. 169, pp.10-12, 1941).

Another phenomenon evident from these requests is the fact that a large number of them come from Albanian refugees from Kosovo and other areas inhabited by Albanians in the former Kingdom of Yugoslavia. Since the First Balkan War, the First World War, and in the 1920s–1930s, many Albanian refugees from Yugoslavia come to Albania, where they experience economic difficulties, as they have left their lands and possessions. A part of them have come with their families to Albania and have settled on some state lands or lands obtained with the kingdom's agrarian reform, but a good part, especially fighters, have come alone and are in the streets without any economic help. This is why these former fighters request shelter in the old people's house in Shkodër. In addition to the usual reasons for poverty and lack of relatives to take care of them, the refugees from Kosovo or Dibra also mention that they have fought for the national cause, or that they have left their lands persecuted by the Serbs, and have come to seek refuge in the "mother country" (CSA, F: 235, fl. 169, pp.10-12, 1941).

In addition to the people who asked to be admitted to the house for the elderly, beggars are also sent to this institution. Thus, from the municipality of Elbasan,

Durrës, Berat, there are requests addressed to the Red Cross Directorate to place some beggars, mainly women, who wander the streets in these cities. Among other things, this is because the legislation of the time prohibits public begging, and local authorities are obliged to stop beggars, but on the other hand, they have to provide assistance for their survival. Thus, in the cases of the elderly, it is a solution to send them to this institution (CSA, F: 272, fl.295, pp.17-25, 1941). Another source of candidates is the state hospital: elderly or disabled persons, who are sheltered in hospitals with contagious diseases or serious illnesses, and who could no longer be kept in the hospital after their treatment, are sent to the house for the elderly in Shkodër. A regulation, which seems to have been rigorously implemented regarding elderly with contagious diseases, is that the latter are not accepted in old people's houses. Thus, there are communications between the municipalities, the Red Cross Directorate and the State Hospital, in which it appears that sick beggars who are sent by the municipality to shelter in the old people's house and are identified as having contagious diseases, are sent for treatment in the State Hospital, then they are admitted to the old people's house (CSA, F:203, fl. 944, pp.20-30, 1940).

Due to the great needs of the population and the limited financial opportunities of the Red Cross, the limited places in the old people's house in Shkodër are quickly occupied. In September 1941, there are no more places in this elders' house and applications are rejected even if they are eligible. This is evident from the request of an elderly woman from Elbasan to be sheltered in this institution with the relevant certificates of the municipality and the prefecture, but the Red Cross Directorate replies that the old women could not be accepted because there are no places in it (CSA, F: 272, fl.295, pp.17-25, 1941).

The years 1940–1941 are difficult in Albania and Italy, as it is the period of the Italian-Greek War, which Italy is losing until the intervention of Germany from Yugoslavia. Thus, the shelter for the elderly is out of the attention of the central institutions. Nevertheless, the staff of the old people's house is completed in this period and it consists of a director, a doctor, a nurse, three caregivers, a cook and an assistant-cook, a butler and an ambulance driver. A special care is given to the doctor and the nurse of the nursing house: as the director of the institution states in the documents, most of the elderly are chronically ill and need constant care.

Also, from the purchase receipts at the old people's house it appears that the institution has continuous heating with wood stoves, their menu includes meat, vegetables, rice, sugar, pasta, oil, milk, cheese, eggs, coffee or surrogates. Tobacco, medicines, shoes and clothes are regularly bought for the inhabitants to be presentable, they are also offered haircuts at the barber. An additional concern of the Directorate of the institution is the care for infectious diseases, as they are considered to be very dangerous. Thus, not only are the patients with uncured infectious diseases not admitted, but also the elderly members of the institution are given occasional check-ups, so that they should not have a problem with those diseases (CSA, F: 203, fl.943, pp.1-24, 1942).

Thus, it can be said that even during the Italian-Greek War, when the government concentrates all its attention on this war and is experiencing a food crisis, the house for the elderly is not completely left out of attention and the Directorate of the Red Cross generally meets the institution's requirements. This is also related to the general

social policy of the Italians in Albania, who, as mentioned above, alleviate poverty and social wounds in the country – certainly for their own purposes, but nevertheless for the benefit of the population as well. One shortcoming of this analysis is that the data on the living conditions of the elderly in this institution are based on indirect documents such as invoices for the purchase of goods or services, and it cannot be declared exactly whether the elderly received those goods and services, since during the war there are no inspections from the Red Cross Directorate for this institution, as well as there are no first-hand testimonies of the living conditions in them.

Discussion and conclusions

This article aimed to deal with the first establishment and operation of a house for the elderly in Albania during the period of the Kingdom, which is later concretized during the Italian occupation of the country. First is given a history of social care in the country, exercised by religious institutions or wealthy individuals during the last period of the Ottoman Empire and the beginnings of the Albanian state. During the period of the Albanian state's consolidation, there is a significant decrease in private charitable activity, which forces the state bodies to take measures to alleviate social wounds. The first measures are taken to build and maintain a children's house, as well as the provision of food and health care for the poor and the elderly in public hospitals. In 1936, the Ministry of the Interior begins actions to establish a house for the elderly, which is completed in 1938 with a royal decree, based on which an institution for the elderly is established and its budget is secured. These actions of the royal government continue even during the Italian occupation, when in July 1940 the first house for the elderly is founded in Shkodër. They accept elderly people over 60 years old, without any relatives, without means of living and who could not work anymore. The establishment and maintenance of this institution relies on public taxes, collected directly for this institution.

In the elders' house in Shkodër there are three sections, one for women, one for men and one for children up to four years old. A special attention is paid to health care for the elderly, as well as to the control of infectious diseases. This is done by a doctor and a nurse as part of the staff. If the food purchases and the services paid by the institution for the elderly are examined, it can be seen that their treatment was relatively good for the conditions of the time. However, these are state documents and examining the perspective of the elderly regarding this treatment is now impossible, so it cannot be said with complete certainty what their treatment or their relationship with the staff. Nevertheless, what should be noted is that the state bodies have not ignored the demands of this institution even in this period of political instability.

If the approach of the Albanian state in the period of the Kingdom but also the approach of the Quisling government in relation to social care for the elderly is analysed, according to the features mentioned above (Daly & Lewis, 2000), it can be observed that in the concept of the Albanian state institutions the main provider for social care for the elderly is the family or their relatives. This appears first in the Civil Code that children are responsible for supporting their parents and even

elderly relatives with whom they live in the same house. Also, in the regulation of old people's houses, it is determined that only the elderly who are alone, without relatives and without means of living, are accepted. Only for them, the state institutions provide social care.

The state aims, but with little or no success, charitable institutions, religious or secular, to alleviate the social wounds, but as this is not the case, the state is forced to take over this task (Hoxha, 2011, p. 57)

Regarding the question of who pays for the social care, the main idea of the Albanian state is that the family or the individual would pay for it. This is because the main provider is considered the family, within which expenses would be borne. The individual also has a role, so even if you are lonely but have wealth or other means of living, you could not be admitted to these institutions. As for the service provided by the state in those institutions that are expected to be established, or after they are established, the payment would be borne by the public through taxes. This is an element, although very limited, where the Albanian state shows features of welfare state, as through special taxes the public pays for the elders' care.

Throughout this period (it continues until the 1970s during socialism) social care provided by the state in Albania is not considered a 'service' that could be 'sold' in exchange for payment. Therefore, a wealthy individual who would like to be admitted to the institution for care, even in exchange for payment, is unable to do so.

In relation to the infrastructure, the means by which the social care provided by the state is realized, this is more complex, because initially, due to the lack of infrastructure, the poor elderly are only given food in the Red Cross canteens, while after the establishment of the house for the elderly, they are offered full service in this state institution. However, during the Italian occupation many public canteens are opened, even poor citizens could eat food in army canteens, so the infrastructure is complex.

To summarize, by analysing all the above-mentioned elements, the key concept of the Albanian state is that the family is the main provider of the elders' social care. Social care offered by the state institutions is limited only for a few individuals who are lonely, disabled and without any income. However, it should be considered that even in a period of strong economic crisis and political instability, state institutions try to soften the social burdens in Albania.

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ESTABLISHMENT AND OPERATION OF THE FIRST ELDERS' CARE INSTITUTION IN ALBANIA

Inxhi Brisku

Abstract

This article analyses the efforts for establishing and operating the first elders' care institutions in Albania during the monarchical regime of Ahmet Zogu and the fascist occupation. Based on archival documents, a detailed description is given of the Albanian authorities' efforts to found a care institution for the elderly, of the taxes collected for this purpose, of the negotiations between the central and the local institutions during the process, of the justifications encouraging the payments of those taxes made by the state representatives.

In addition, a comparative analysis is offered of the main dimensions of the social care with the social care conceptualized and provided by the Albanian state. The concept of social care is broader than that only for the elderly, but in this article, only social care for the elderly is considered. The basic concept of the Albanian state is that the main provider of elders' social care is the family. Only a few individuals, who do not have family or stable incomes, should be taken care of by the state institutions and their care would be paid through special taxes.

Key words: Albanian state, family, elders' social care, first elders' care institution

СЪЗДАВАНЕ И ФУНКЦИОНИРАНЕ НА ПЪРВАТА ИНСТИТУЦИЯ ЗА ГРИЖИ ЗА ВЪЗРАСТНИ ХОРА В АЛБАНИЯ

Инджи Бриску

Резюме

Тази статия анализира усилията за създаване и функциониране на първите институции за грижи за възрастни хора в Албания по време на монархическия режим на Ахмет Зогу и фашистката окупация. Въз основа на архивни документи е дадено подробно описание на усилията на албанските власти да създадат институция за грижи за възрастни хора, на данъците, събирани за тази цел, на преговорите между централните и местните институции по време на процеса, на обосновките за насърчаване на плащанията на тези данъци, направени от държавните представители.

Освен това се предлага сравнение между основните измерения на социалните грижи и социалните грижи, концептуализирани и предоставяни от албанската държава. Понятието социалните грижи е по-широко и включва понятието „социални грижи за възрастни хора“, но в тази статия се разглеждат само социални грижи за възрастни хора. Основната концепция на албанската държава е, че главен доставчик на социални грижи за възрастните хора е семейството. Само лица, които нямат семейни или стабилни доходи, трябва да бъдат обгрижвани от държавните институции и грижите за тях да се плащат чрез специални данъци.

Ключови думи: Албания, семейство, институции за грижи за възрастни хора

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